

Supplemental Table 1: Primer sequences for qRT-PCR and murine Sost 3' UTR cloning

Gene	Primer sequence 5'-3'
<i>Rankl/Tnfsf11</i>	Forward CCA AGA TCT CTA ACA TGA CG
	Reverse CAC CAT CAG CTG AAG ATA GT
<i>Opg/Tnfrsf11b</i>	Forward AGT CCG TGA AGC AGG AGT
	Reverse CCA TCT GGA CAT TTT TTG CAA A
<i>Axin2</i>	Forward GCA GCA GAT CCG GGA GGA TGA A
	Reverse GAT TGA CAG CCG GGG GTC TTG A
<i>Wnt16</i>	Forward CGG ATG ATG TCC AGT ACG GC
	Reverse CAT TAA CTT GGC GAC AGC CTG C
<i>Dkk1</i>	Forward GAT CTG TCT GGC TTG CCG AA
	Reverse TTC CCC TCG AGG AAA ATG GC
<i>Sost</i>	Forward GGC AAG CCT TCA GGA ATG ATG
	Reverse TGT ACT CGG ACA CAT CTT TGG C
<i>Lif</i>	Forward TTG CAT GGT AGC GGC TTC AG
	Reverse ATT TGT CAC CCA AGG CCA AGT C
<i>Rpl38</i>	Forward AGA ACA AGG ATA ATG TGA AGT TCA AGG TTC
	Reverse CTG CTT CAG CTT CTC TGC CTT T
Sost 3'UTR cloning	Forward TTC TAC ACT AGT GCG CGA TCC GAT TCG TTT TCA GTG
	Reverse TTC TAC CAC G CGT TAT TAA CAA TGC CTC TGG TCG GGG A

Wild type

Col1a1-miR-433TuD

LysM-creX miR-29TuD

Supplemental Figure 1. The Col1a1^{miR-433TuD} is not expressed in the osteoclast lineage.

Differential interference contrast images overlaid by tdTomato signal in primary bone marrow monocytes cultured with MCSF+RANKL (30 ng/ml each) for 4 days. (Top) cells from wild type mice. (Middle) cells from Col1a1^{miR-433TuD} mice. (Bottom) cells from mice expressing LysM-cre and cre-activated tdTomato-miR-29 TuD cassette knocked into the Rosa26 locus, as described in (57,58). Cells expressing the miR-433-3p TuD or miR-29-3p TuD will be marked by tdTomato expression, which is seen only in cells with LysM-cre mediated activation of the tdTomato-miR-29 TuD. Same exposure for all images; arrows=osteoclast; *=artifact; scale bar – 50 μm